

ELABORATION AND MECHANICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF FLAX-PCL COMPOSITES AND SANDWICHES

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ABSTRACT

Flax composites have been manufactured with polycaprolactone (PCL) matrix in order to obtain biodegradable composites. Flax fibers assembled in unidirectional fabrics and flax shives have been used as different reinforcements. Flax shives are a co-product obtained during flax fibers extraction by combing.

UD flax-PCL composites give mechanical properties comparable to other matrices tested with UD flax. Besides the potential biodegradability, PCL is interesting to use because optimal elaboration temperature was found at 90°C. It allows to maintain a part of water content inside flax fibers and to avoid a prior drying step of flax fibers.

Flax shives-PCL composites give lower mechanical properties than UD flax-PCL ones: 1/8 for stiffness and 1/50 for strength. These results emphasize the possibility of using shive-PCL combination as a core for sandwich structures with flax fiber composites.

Elaboration of sandwich samples shows the difficulty to use a one step process during which both faces and core are created. Instead, a process with a preliminary elaboration of core has been successful. However, sandwich samples present an increase of density of the core compared to the shives-PCL composites.

Flexural properties of sandwich parts have been evaluated to determine equivalent shear and flexural stiffnesses. Obtained values are consistent with theoretical approach. Equivalent shear rigidity could certainly be improved whereas experimental value of equivalent flexural rigidity is higher than the predicted one. Rupture of sandwich samples appears in the core or at the bond between core and faces. All these flexural results confirm that these sandwich materials have a potential and that core is probably the component to optimise. Some comparisons with comparable sandwich structures (with balsa, foams or honeycombs) should be undertaken to confirm this interest.

1 INTRODUCTION

Flax composites merges among plant fiber composites because of the intrinsic mechanical properties of their fibers. This is mainly due to the small angle of cellulose microfibrils to the longitudinal fiber axis. Moreover, an industrial sector dedicated to the extraction of fibers from the stem of the plant - retting and scutching - already exists for textile production. Flax is the third plant fiber produced in the world after cotton and jute.

A lot of matrices have been tested for flax composites including thermosetting resins (epoxy, polyester, etc.) and thermoplastics (polypropylene, polyamide, polyethylene, etc.). Flax composites take more interest if they are associated with biosourced and/or biodegradable polymers. Attempts with partially biosourced thermosets (usually around 50% biosourced) or biodegradable thermoplastics like Polylactic Acid (PLA) have been achieved with good mechanical performances. However, PLA has a melting temperature over 150°C. Flax fibers contained around 8-10% of water so use of PLA induces evaporation of this water during the manufacturing of composites or a prior drying of flax fibers.

Polycaprolactone (PCL) is a highly biodegradable polymer (according to EN 13432) which has the advantage over PLA to melt at 60°C so it can be processed in the range 60-100°C for flax composites. Moreover, PCL compared to PLA is highly ductile, more resistant at low temperatures (glass transition temperature at -60°C) and resistant to moisture (less than 1% of water content).

This study is undertaken to confirm the interest of using PCL with flax products in order to achieve original properties for flax composites and sandwiches.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Reinforcements

A UniDirectional (called UD1) Non-Crimp Fabric (NCF) with areal weight at 290 g.m⁻² is compared to a woven quasi-UD (called UD2) with M_s = 205 g.m⁻².

Flax shives consist in the woody core of flax stem generated as a by-product from the flax scutching process. Their dimensions vary from 2mm to 20 mm for length, from 1mm to 2mm for width and from 0.1mm to 1 mm for thickness. Flax shives used in this work are manufactured by Depestele (https://www.groupepestele.com/pro_paillis.html).

2.2 PCL matrix

Capa™ 6506 (from company Perstop) is a high molecular weight linear polyester derived from caprolactone monomer [1]. It is supplied in powder form and therefore allows an association with the flax fabrics under a press. Its given melting temperature is about 59 °C and its melt flow index is about 7. Its degradation temperature is over 300°C. It gives a wide range of temperatures for elaboration of composites. Its density is given at 1.1g.cm⁻³ (at 60°C) by the provider.

2.3 Composites and sandwiches elaboration

For composite or sandwich elaboration, flax fabrics (155*290mm²) and/or flax shives are stacked with Capa 6506 powder inside a mold heated by induction (Roctool technology - <http://www.roctool.com/>) and cooled down by a system of circulating water. This process allows a faster composite elaboration than classical heated presses. Pressure value is imposed at values between 2.0 and 3.0MPa before and during heating. Exposure at 90°C is chosen at 5 min for flax fiber composites and at 10 min for shives composites and sandwich parts. Upward ramp to attain 90°C is about 20s and downward ramp, around 5 min. The parts were always demolded at 30°C. This procedure allows to attain a flax fiber content inside composite parts of 50% w/w without visible porosities.

During elaboration, the temperature of 90°C permits to maintain water inside flax fibers. Initial water content inside flax fibers is usually evaluated between 8 and 10%. Preliminary tests at 100°C showed that some bubbles appear in the matrix. They probably come from evaporation of water contained in fibers or shives. Use of PCL at 90°C has therefore the great advantage to avoid a pre-heating of flax.

Composites were elaborated by stacking a ply and the corresponding quantity of PCL powder over it, then a ply, etc. Thickness of final composites is usually around 2mm.

Sandwich elaboration has been tested with two methods. The first one can be called 'one step process'. It consists in stacking the flax fiber plies of the below face with the necessary amount of PCL between each ply, then the shives and PCL powder melt together and finally the plies of the upper face with PCL. The whole stack is then pressed according to the procedure adopted in the first paragraph of this section. The result is not satisfying, especially because of irregularities observed on both faces such as roughness and distortions of UD fabrics. The second method involves two steps: firstly, flax shives and PCL are pressed to manufacture the core; secondly, flax fabrics and PCL are placed from either side of the core and pressed to form both faces and the sandwich simultaneously. It resulted better than the first method because of the regularity of the preformed core as a rectangular parallelepiped.

2.4 Mechanical characterization

Composite samples are prepared by waterjet cutting from composite plates then stocked at 25°C and 50% relative humidity during one week. Tensile tests are done as according to ISO 527 over at least three samples for each composite and 1mm/min velocity.

Shives composites and sandwich samples are cut with a scroll saw. 3-points flexion tests are performed with NF T54-606 norm (AFNOR). Length of samples is varied in order to obtain the equivalent flexural rigidity (D in $N.mm^2$) and the equivalent shear rigidity (N in Newtons). So span length, l , is defined as 10 or 20 times the total thickness of the sandwich, d . Experimental l values are about 120mm and 60mm for flexural rigidity and shear rigidity respectively. For each sandwich sample, the deflection δ under the load P corresponding to half the rupture load is extracted. An average of these values is done for each span length (l and l') and is used in the following equation system:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\delta}{P} = \frac{l^3}{48D} + \frac{l}{4N} \\ \frac{\delta'}{P'} = \frac{l'^3}{48D} + \frac{l'}{4N} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

At least five samples were tested either for traction or for flexion tests.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Elaborated parts

According to the process parameters, composite parts are obtained with 53% w/w of fibers for UD1, 50% w/w for UD2 and 80% w/w for shives.

UD1 and UD2 composites do not show visible porosities whereas shives composites have a density of 0.509 g.cm^{-3} . A good impregnation by the viscous PCL is possible because shives composites are well aggregated. It remains more than 50% of porosity inside shive composites. Porosity can be found inside and between the shives.

Sandwich parts (SAPCL2 and SAPCL4) obtained with the two-step's method of elaboration (see section 2.3) possess the dimensional and physical characteristics described in Table 1. Difference between SAPCL2 and SAPCL4 is mainly in faces thickness, t . In SAPCL2, there is one ply of UD1 and it gives $t = 0.40\text{mm}$ whereas, in SAPCL4, two plies of UD1 are present with $t = 0.80 \text{ mm}$. It is important to notice here that faces thickness is estimated from flax and PCL weights and densities and considering that no porosities occur in the faces. This ultimate assumption is consistent with observations on composite parts.

Table 1 shows that estimated core density is higher than the density achieved for flax shives composites (0.824 and 0.846 g.cm^{-3} against 0.509 g.cm^{-3} respectively). Moreover, sandwich parts are elaborated under lighter pressures (2.12MPa) than shives composites (2.65MPa). Only two factors can explain this result: i) pressure is exerted during 10 min at 90°C for core elaboration plus 10 min during sandwich elaboration whereas only 10 min for shives composites. A higher relaxation could occur during sandwich fabrication while pressure value is constantly maintained; ii) the presence of flax fabrics during sandwich fabrication could result in a higher compaction of the core.

Table 1 also shows that sandwich thickness increases between SAPCL2 and SAPCL4 proportionally to the increase from 1 ply to 2 plies of UD1 in both faces.

			SAPCL2	SAPCL4
PCL 1 face weight		g	12.15	24.3
Flax 1 face weight		g	12.15	24.3
PCL core weight		g	38.4	38.4
Flax shives core weight		g	153	153
Sandwich thickness	d	mm	5.97	6.63
1 face thickness	t	mm	0.40	0.80
Core thickness*	c	mm	5.17	5.03
Core density	ρ_c	$\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$	0.824	0.846

Table 1: Dimensional and physical characteristics of obtained sandwich parts. (*: core thickness is obtained by subtracting the estimated 2 faces thickness from the measured total thickness)

3.2 Tensile tests

Longitudinal tensile tests over PCL-flax UD composites give curves with a first curvature part followed by a quasi-linear part until rupture. These curves look very similar to the ones from tensile tests over flax fibers [2] as illustrated on Fig.1. The fragile rupture of PCL-UD composites can be explained by the low tensile strength of PCL (around 20MPa according [3]) and a PCL strain at break of 4.5%.

Fig. 1. Comparison between a flax composite tensile curve from this work (on the left) and a flax fiber tensile curve (on the right) from [2].

UD2 gives better results for both modulus and for tensile strength than UD1. The NCF UD1 is composed of a layer of aligned fibers whereas UD2 is well divided in yarns. This may explain an easier impregnation between the yarns in UD2 than in UD1 and therefore more interesting tensile properties.

Fig. 2. Tensile properties of flax fibers and shives composites

3.2 Flexural tests

3-points flexural tests over both sandwich parts have shown similar failure modes either with short or long span lengths. Observed failure modes are either core failure or bond failure or mixed core-bond failure. Shear strength was calculated for short span length, giving values around 1 MPa (see Table 2).

From Equation (1) and experimental curves, equivalent shear stiffness and equivalent flexural stiffness are deduced. Values are reported in Table 2.

			SAPCL2	SAPCL4
Sandwich thickness	d	mm	5.97	6.63
Equivalent shear stiffness	N	Newtons	5722	6219
Equivalent flexural stiffness	D	N.mm ²	2.99E+06	1.24E+07
Shear strength	τ	MPa	0.839	1.038

Table 2: 3-points flexural test results.

3 DISCUSSION ABOUT SANDWICH STIFFNESS

According to Gibson-Ashby approach [4], the optimized sandwich structure in weight with a stiffness objective should be such as “the ratio of the weight of the two faces to that of the core” is 1/4 whatever the materials, loading conditions, geometry of the beam, etc. SAPCL2 sample has been elaborated according to this principle and SAPCL4 sample achieves a ratio about 1/2. The principles developed in [4] also shows that “the ratio of the bending component of deflection to the shear component” should be 1/2. Considering the definitions of these both components, it gives:

$$l_{optimal} = \sqrt{\frac{6D}{N}} \quad (2)$$

where $l_{optimal}$ is the optimal span length.

For SAPCL2, $l_{optimal} = 55$ mm and for SAPCL4, $l_{optimal} = 109$ mm. It means that N and D obtained values are consistent in proportion.

Equivalent shear stiffness can be used to determine the shear modulus of the core, G_c^* :

$$N = \frac{bd^2}{c} G_c^* \quad (3)$$

with b , sandwich width. Geometrical parameters are known so shear modulus can be determined: its average value over SAPCL2 and SAPCL4 is about 40MPa. This value can be compared to fiberboards (for example, wood particles-phenol formaldehyde composites) one: around 200MPa according CES 2018 software. G_c^* value for flax sandwiches should be optimized by adjusting parameters such as proportion of PCL and shives, compression of the core, etc.

Equivalent flexural stiffness can be calculated from:

$$D = \frac{bt^3}{6} E_f + \frac{bc^3}{12} E_c + \frac{btd^2}{2} E_f \quad (4)$$

with E_f , face modulus and E_c , core modulus. These last parameters are known from section 3.2. and can be used to determine theoretical values of D. For SAPCL2, $D = 1.07 \cdot 10^6$ N.mm² and for SAPCL4, $D = 2.32 \cdot 10^6$ N.mm². These values are lower than the experimental ones given in Table 2.

9 CONCLUSIONS

The difference of tensile properties between flax fiber composites and flax shive composites make them interesting to develop sandwich structures. The idea developed in the present approach is to use flax shives and PCL as a core. Flax shives are a co-product of flax fibers extraction and should be a good candidate to replace balsa or polymeric honeycombs.

Primary results on flax-PCL sandwich stiffness show that this type of materials seems to respect the classical formalism developed by Gibson and Ashby [4]. More sandwich samples should be tested by varying different parameters: PCL core content, core density, flax fiber content in the faces, etc.

Further studies of PCL-flax sandwiches could be also undertaken for optimizing strength and impact properties and detect the differences and characteristics of PCL-flax sandwiches from classical combinations of foam-synthetic fibers composites.

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